

Full Length Research Paper

Pharmacological evidence favouring the ethnomedicinal use of *Luffa cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaf in the relief of pain and fever

*Saliu, O. A.¹, Akanji, M. A.², Idowu, O. A.² and Saliu, N. B.³

¹Department of Environmental Health Science, Faculty of Health Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.

²Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Ilorin, Ilorin Kwara State, P.M.B 1515, Ilorin, Nigeria.

³National Universities Commission, Abuja, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author E-mail: remisaliu@yahoo.com

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A study to investigate the ethnobotanical use of *Luffa cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaf in pain and fever relief was carried out. Methanolic extract was obtained from leaves of *Luffa cylindrica* and was subjected to phytochemical screening using standard procedure of Trease and Evans, (1989). Analgesic effect of the plant was carried out by inducing pain in mice in the form of abdominal constriction using glacial acetic acid. The antipyretic property of the plant was also investigated in rats by yeast-induced pyrexia. Phytochemical analysis of methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* leaves revealed the presence of saponins, tannins, phenolics, alkaloids, triterpenes, flavonoids and cardiac glycosides in appreciable amounts. The extract showed a

significant ($p < 0.05$) inhibition of abdominal constriction in mice induced with pain sensation in a dose-dependent manner. Antipyretic activity of the plant was evident by a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in rectal temperature at all investigated doses (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight) and was time dependent. Methanolic extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves exhibited potent analgesic and antipyretic activities which therefore supports the ethnopharmacological use of the plant.

Keywords: *Luffa cylindrica*, acetic acid, acetylsalicylic acid, paracetamol, methanol

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have been used for centuries as remedies to cure different ailments of mankind because they contain components of therapeutic values. Phytochemicals which are considered as secondary metabolite components are directly responsible for the medicinal activities of plants. These include antioxidant, antimicrobial, antifungal, anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities (Kakate, 1997). Approximately 80% of people in developing countries depend on traditional medicine for primary health care (Bashal and

Sudarsanam, 2012). Application of traditional herbal medicine to treat various ailments, infections, diseases as well as in maintaining the physical and psychological wellbeing of a large number of people have been in existence for many decades. Traditional herbal medicine include all kinds of folk medicine, unconventional medicine and indeed any kind of therapeutic methods used locally by people for the treatment of different ailments. In Nigeria, more than 60% of the populace in the rural areas depends on traditional medicine for

treatment of different kind of illnesses (Ghani *et al.*, 1989). Various parts of plants are prepared locally either as concoction or decoction to treat ailments. Also some medicinal plants have been used as source of inspiration for the development of novel drugs (Robbers and Tylor, 1996). Most plants that are locally used are relatively safer than the synthetic alternatives; they are readily available, cheaper and work effectively without side effect (Iwu *et al.*, 1999). Despite the milestone recorded, the full potential of plants is yet to be fully exhausted. A typical example is *Luffa cylindrica* which has been reported to have ethnomedicinal values but the pharmacological basis for the ethnomedicinal use is yet to be documented.

Description of *Luffa cylindrica*

Luffa cylindrica (L.) Roem commonly called sponge gourd is a vegetable that belongs to the family of Cucurbitacea. It is a sub-tropical plant that requires warm summer temperature and also well cultivated in tropical countries in Asia and Africa. The leaves are alternate and palmately lobed, of a light green color and almost destitute of taste. The flowers are monoecious, petals five, united below into a bell shaped corolla; anthers cohering in a mass; ovary two celled, style slender, stigmas three, both male and female flowers are on the same plant and are pollinated by bees. The fruit is elliptical ovate, fleshy and dehiscent with a green epidermis, longitudinally marked with black ridges varying from 10-15 in a number. Under each of these ridges is found a tough woody fiber.

Ethnomedicinal use of *Luffa cylindrica*

In Nigeria, the decoction of the plant leaves is consumed locally to treat malaria (Azeez *et al.*, 2013). There are also report on the local use of the leaves of the plant to treat wounds (Azeez *et al.*, 2013), fever and jaundice (Neuwinger, 2000), and to alleviate pain and inflammation (Khan *et al.*, 2013). However, there is paucity information on the scientific validation of the analgesic and antipyretic properties of the plant. This study therefore probes into the analgesic and antipyretic activities of *L. cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaves.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant collection

Fresh leaves of *Luffa cylindrica* (L.) Roem were collected from Suleja, Niger State at early hours in the month of July, 2015. The plant was authenticated at National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), Abuja with voucher number (6650) deposited in

the herbarium of the institute.

Preparation of plant extract

The leaves of *L. cylindrica* (L.) Roem were air-dried and pulverized with mechanical blender (Mazeda Mill, MT 4100, Japan). 500 g of the pulverized leaves was macerated in 1 litre of absolute methanol (99%) for 72 h with concomitant shaking using a stirrer. The resulting extract was filtered with cotton wool and with Whatman (No. 1) paper respectively. The filtrate obtained was concentrated in a rotary evaporator (RE-300B model, China) at 60 – 65°C and was dried to a constant weight on a water bath to give a yield of 28% (w/w). The extract was reconstituted into appropriate concentrations used for analgesic and antipyretic experiments.

Experimental animals

Both sexes of Swiss Albino mice (24.0 - 26.0 g) and Wistar rats (180 – 250 g) were used for analgesic and antipyretic study respectively. The animals were bred in the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), Abuja, Nigeria. They were housed in cages under 12:12 h light/dark cycle conditions and were fed with commercial pellet (Platinum Feed Mills Company, Nigeria) and had water *ad libitum*.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval for using the experimental animals was issued by the University of Ilorin Ethical Committee on the use of experimental animals.

Drugs and chemicals

Methanol, glacial acetic acid (Searle, England), aspirin (Sigma, USA) and paracetamol used in this study were obtained commercially.

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical constituents in the methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* leaves were screened by standard screening procedure described by Trease and Evans, (1989). Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, anthraquinones, triterpenes, phenolic, phlobatannins and cardiac glycosides were determined qualitatively and quantitatively.

Acetic acid induced writhing in mice

Acetic acid was used to induce abdominal constriction (writhes) in mice according to the method of Koster *et al.*

Table 1. Secondary metabolites of methanolic extract off *Luffa cylindrica* leaf.

Secondary metabolites	Composition mg/g
Saponins	0.98 ± 0.03
Tannins	3.58 ± 0.90
Anthraquinones	ND
Triterpenes	17.45 ± 2.16
Phenolic	9.16 ± 0.12
Flavonoids	7.45 ± 0.49
Alkaloids	11.35 ± 0.07
Phlobatannins	ND
Cardaic glycosides	0.05 ± 0.01

(1959). Mice were grouped into five groups consisting of five mice each and treated as follows: Group I served as the control and received appropriate volume of distilled water, group II, III and IV received 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg b.w of the extract respectively and group V served as the reference group administered 100 mg/kg b.w acetylsalicylic acid (ASA). Administration of vehicle and extract was done intraperitoneally (i.p). After 30 min of administration of water/extract/standard drug, 10 ml/kg of 0.75% aqueous solution of acetic acid was injected i.p to each rat to cause pain sensation. Each mouse was gently housed in a transparent cage and after 5 min of post-administration of acetic acid, the number of abdominal constrictions for each mouse was counted using a manual table counter for 10 min. % inhibition of writhes was calculated using the expression:

$$\text{Percentage pain inhibition} = \frac{\text{Control mean} - \text{Test mean}}{\text{Control mean}} \times 100$$

Yeast-induced pyrexia (fever)

The antipyretic activity of the extract was investigated in rats by adopting the method described by Al-Ghamdi, (2001). The rats were injected subcutaneously with 10 ml/kg of 15% suspension of yeast in distilled water to induce pyrexia. The rectal temperature of each rat was measured 24 h before and after yeast injection with a clinical thermometer respectively. Rats that did not show minimum increase of 0.5°C in temperature 24 h post-yeast injection were discarded. Twenty five selected rats were grouped into five (n=5) and treated as follows: Group 1 received distilled water and 10 ml/kg saline, groups 2, 3 and 4 received the extract at a dose of 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg b.w respectively while group 5 received 20 mg/kg b.w of paracetamol which served as the reference drug group. The rectal temperature of each rat was repeatedly measured at 30 min intervals for 120 min post-treatment.

Statistical data analysis

Two ways ANOVA was used to analyze and compare

means data, followed by Dunnet's test for multiple comparisons.

RESULTS

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical analysis of methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaves indicated the presence of alkaloids (11.35 ± 0.07 mg/g), flavonoids (7.45 ± 0.49 mg/g), phenolic (9.16 ± 0.12 mg/g), cardiac glycosides (0.05 ± 0.01 mg/g), triterpenes (17.45 ± 2.16 mg/g), tannins (3.58 ± 0.90 mg/g) and saponins (0.98 ± 0.03 mg/g). Triterpenes was the most predominantly secondary metabolites found in the extract followed by alkaloids while cardiac glycosides were the least (Table 1).

Analgesic effect

Methanolic leaf extract of *L. cylindrica* (L.) Roem significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the degree of abdominal constriction induced in mice by the administration of acetic acid intraperitoneally at all investigated doses and was dose-dependent. It was observed that 100 mg/kg b.w of the extract showed the lowest writhing/pain inhibition (52.38%) while 400 mg/kg showed the most potent inhibition (61.42%). The extract at 400 mg/kg b.w also demonstrated a comparable inhibition of abdominal constriction with acetylsalicylate (ASA) adopted as the standard drug in this study which elicited 77.21% inhibition activity (Table 2).

Antipyretic effect

Table 3 depicts the antipyretic effect of administration of methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaves in rats. The crude extract caused a significant alteration ($p < 0.05$) in rectal temperature of rats at the three doses investigated by markedly lowering the rectal temperature 30 min post-treatment of the extract when compared with

Table 2. Effect of methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* leaves on acetic acid-induced writhing in mice.

Treatment (i.p)	No of writhing	% inhibition
Control	23.33 ± 3.84	-
100 mg/kg b.w MELC	11.11 ± 0.33	52.38*
200 mg/kg b.w MELC	10.43 ± 1.20	55.29*
400 mg/kg b.w MELC	9.00 ± 3.06	61.42*
ASP (100 mg/kg b.w)	8.67 ± 0.58	62.84*

The results given are mean ± S.E.M in five replicates; *p < 0.05 as compared to control groups
ASP – acetylsalicylate, MELC – methanolic leaf extract of *L. cylindrica*, i.p - intraperitoneal

Table 3. Effect of methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* leaves on yeast-induced pyrexia in rats.

Treatment (i.p)	Dose (mg/kg)	Rectal temperature (°C)				
		-24	0 h	0.5 h	1 h	2 h
Saline(10ml/kg)	-	37.20 ± 0.12	38.73 ± 0.90	39.70 ± 0.12	39.23 ± 0.19	39.20 ± 0.06
MELC	100	37.43 ± 0.26	38.70 ± 0.53	38.30 ± 0.13*	38.12 ± 0.12*	37.50 ± 0.06*
MELC	200	37.40 ± 0.27	39.10 ± 0.20	37.77 ± 0.09*	37.53 ± 0.22*	36.73 ± 0.09*
MELC	400	37.43 ± 0.24	38.97 ± 0.44	37.50 ± 0.23*	37.33 ± 0.15*	36.50 ± 0.20*
Paracetamol	20	37.37 ± 0.03	38.40 ± 0.31	37.27 ± 0.17*	37.13 ± 0.09*	36.37 ± 0.15*

The results given are mean ± S.E.M in five replicates; *p < 0.05 as compared to control groups
MELC – methanolic leaf extract of *L. cylindrica*

the saline group. The rectal temperature was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lowered in a time dependent manner at treated doses. Similar trend was also observed in the group administered paracetamol. The extract at 400 mg/kg b.w of the extract exhibited the most remarkable antipyretic activity.

DISCUSSION

The phytochemical constituents detected in the methanolic extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaves in this study have been reported to be present in methanolic fruits extract of this plant (Fahima *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, they have also been reported to be present in the leaf extract of this plant collected from Adamawa State in North-eastern part of Nigeria (Etim *et al.*, 2018). This may indicate that these secondary metabolites could be predominantly found in almost all parts of the plants. The analgesic potential of the extract was studied by using acetic acid to induce writhing model, a type of visceral pain model in experimental animals. Abdominal writhing or constriction is a form of pain characterized with stretching behavior in animals induced by nociceptive agents like acetic acid. The mechanism of action of acetic acid is known to cause writhing usually by increasing fluids of prostaglandin PGE2 and PGF2 α (Deraedt *et al.*, 1980) at peritoneal receptors (Bentley *et al.*, 1983).

Acetic acid may also acts indirectly by releasing endogenous substances responsible for exciting the nerve endings and thus causes pain. To suppress pain, conventional therapeutic drugs such as aspirin, ibuprofen, acetaminophen etc are prescribed (Inotai *et*

al., 2010). These drugs though are associated with some side effects; they relieve pain either by blocking or suppressing the production of prostaglandin which mediate pain through the cyclo-oxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2) enzyme pathway (Egesie *et al.*, 2011; Shahraki *et al.*, 2014). The results obtained on acetic acid-induced writhing in mice indicate that the extract, even at a lower dose was capable of reducing pain effectively thus showing analgesic activity. The extract perhaps may have mimicked the mechanism of action of the conventional drugs or exert other mechanism to reduce the pain perception. Similar to this proposed mechanism of action exhibited by the extract, are the reports of Cowan (2007) and Shahraki *et al.* (2014) who gave submission that methanol and ethanol extracts from Aloe vera have been proven to have analgesic activity *in vivo* and *in vitro* respectively by suppressing the expression of cyclo-oxygenase enzymes. The dose-dependent relief of pain perception observed in this study correlates with the reports of Saptarini and Deswati, (2015), Ashfaq *et al.* (2016) and Anisuzzman *et al.* (2017) who also reported a dose-dependent analgesic activity using same model.

Yeast which was used to induce pyrexia in the experimental rats used for this study similarly acts by increasing the production of prostaglandins (PGE2) which mediate fever. The extract was able to lower the rectal temperature observed in the experimental rats possibly by suppressing PGE2 synthesis which may have been facilitated by the presence of flavonoids and other phytoconstituents in the extract. Flavonoids for instance have been reported to cause the inhibition of PGE2 (Robak and Gryglewski, 1996) and as well suppress TNF- α and therefore act as an antipyretic agent

(Adesokan *et al.* 2008). Also Saptarini and Deswati (2015) attributed the antipyretic activity of leaves extract of *Gossypium arboreum* to the presence of flavonoids.

In general, the phytochemical constituents such as flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins or triterpenes among others may be responsible for the analgesic and antipyretic activities exhibited by the extract by acting either separately or synergistically to express these activities.

Conclusion

From this study, the methanolic extract of *L. cylindrica* (L.) Roem leaves reduced abdominal constriction in mice and lowered the rectal temperature of rats. These analgesic and antipyretic activities expressed by the extract may be attributed to the presence of the phytochemical constituents identified in the extract. Most illnesses are characterized with symptoms of either pain or fever or both and natural plant products are locally used to relief these symptoms. The evidence of analgesic and antipyretic activities exhibited by *Luffa cylindrica* might be the pharmacological basis for the ethnobotanical use of the plant to reduce pain and fever.

Authors' declaration

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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